

Pérez-Pueyo, M., Puértolas-Pascual, E., Moreno-Azanza, M., Cruzado-Caballero, P., Gasca, J.M., Canudo, J.I., (2021). First record of a giant bird (Ornithuromorpha) from the uppermost Maastrichtian of the southern Pyrenees,

In the evolutionary history of birds, giant forms have developed in different periods and ecological contexts. In Europe, the first large birds, the Gargantuaviidae, appeared during the Late Cretaceous, and during the Paleogene more groups evolved into large forms. However, until now, no giant birds had been recorded during the terminal Maastrichtian in Europe, near the Cretaceous/Paleogene (K/Pg) boundary when non-avian dinosaurs became extinct. In this study we describe a cervical vertebra from Beranuy (Huesca, NE Spain), which represents the first fossil evidence of a giant bird from the late Maastrichtian of Europe. The microtomography of the vertebra performed at the CENIEH allowed us to reconstruct its cavities, revealing a very large and intricate system of pneumatic cavities, being one of the characteristics that allowed us to assign it to Avialae. This finding demonstrates that large birds were part of the ecological communities of Iberia at the end of the Cretaceous, being present in the last hundreds of thousands of years before the K/Pg mass extinction event.

Figure. Sections obtained from the micro tomography reconstructing the cavities and pneumativity of the studied vertebra MPZ 2019/264. You can see the 3D reconstruction of the vertebra and the cuts made and photographs and diagrams of the fossil.

